

EVENT REPORT
**ATTRACTIVE CAREERS
IN RESEARCH**
2024

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**Event Report 'Attractive Careers in Research:
The Expectations and Roles of Different
Stakeholder Groups'**

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ATTRACTIVE CAREERS IN RESEARCH

**The Expectations & Roles of Different
Stakeholder Groups**

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Introduction

All slides presented during the meeting are available at scieur.org/2024-careers-slides

As part of its strategic priority to contribute to the evolution of research cultures, Science Europe turns its attention to careers in research in 2024–2025. It recognises the pressing need for positive action from both research funding and research performing organisations (RFOs and RPOs) to improve conditions for talented individuals in the European research sector and beyond. This will contribute to the quality of research and evolution of research cultures.

For this purpose, a project was launched that began with a workshop to explore the common and different expectations for careers in research by various stakeholder groups. It also looked at the opportunities for action by RFOs and RPOs that exist, based on these expectations. The perspectives gathered and presented in this report will contribute to a set of practical recommendations by Science Europe, and a platform to support and enable their implementation.

This report summarises the key messages and perspectives gathered during the two-part workshop. It also highlights a series of potential actions that will be discussed further by the Science Europe Task Force on Research Careers. In 2025, the Task Force will prepare a set of recommendations for action by Science Europe Member Organisations, and research organisations more broadly.

To focus on positive actions to improve the conditions for careers in research, it is important to recognise the myriad challenges faced in current research systems across Europe and beyond. Prior to the workshop, a challenge statement was prepared to summarise these issues:

- The **precarity** of research positions, particularly at early career stages, leads to reductions in the attractiveness of academic career pathways and a **loss of talent** to other sectors. Precarity is the result of a **lack of available public funding** for research, the short-term '**projectification**' of research, and a lack of research positions that, combined, lead to an **overly competitive environment**. Competition is a necessary and important element in promoting quality and excellence, yet over-competition acts against promoting high-quality research by increasing talent loss and **reducing diversity** (both in terms of people and ideas). It is vital that actions to improve the conditions for careers in research act on precarity and over-competition without compromising on quality and excellence.
- Broad-scale, international reform of research assessment is underway, yet many of the traditional and **perverse incentives** that have shaped the way that research is conceived, conducted, and communicated remain influential in the careers of research professionals. '**Publish or perish**' remains a well-used idiom, and the focus on **individualistic** and easily quantifiable outputs in research predominate.
- All types of **mobility** within the research system should be recognised as valuable contributions. This includes geographical, virtual, intersectoral, inter-disciplinary, inter-role, and intellectual mobility. Yet, it is also important to recognise that not all roles or positions within the research profession benefit from mobility. Promotion of mobility must focus on and reward the skills and competencies gained, the research results obtained, the outcomes achieved, and coherence with the research strategy, rather than mobility for its own sake. Mobility should not be a requirement for career advancement, where it may introduce or **reinforce unwanted bias** and lead to reductions in equality, diversity, and inclusion.
- As a component of mobility, the international movement of research professionals offers specific benefits and challenges. The **brain drain** of talented individuals from certain regions of the world (or within the European Research Area) seeking more attractive conditions poses significant challenges and will require international collaboration and whole-systems thinking to overcome. The same is true for intersectoral mobility, which is currently heavily skewed towards industry from academia – promoted both by more attractive conditions in the private sector and a **lack of recognition of non-academic skills** and achievements as part of standard research assessment processes.

- Career progression remains **narrowly focused** upon advancement as a function of increasing **leadership**, as is highlighted by the R1–R4 classifications (*Doctoral candidate (R1), junior academic (R2), research fellow (R3), research professor (R4)*). Yet, many important specialised roles in research (lab technicians, science communicators, data scientists, research managers, as examples) would be served better through recognition of increasing skill, experience, and/or competency over increasing leadership.

A selection of key studies, reports, and policy papers that discuss and contextualise the challenges described above, is provided in Annex 2.

Setting the Scene

Over 240 participants from 35 countries and 4 continents participated in the open session of this workshop. Through a Mentimeter poll, participated in by over half of the workshop participants, a range of stakeholders contributed to the discussions:

Which stakeholder group do you represent?

From the Mentimeter participants, there was broad agreement that numerous challenges are faced when thinking about how to improve the attractiveness of careers in research (in line with

the pre-workshop challenge statement), with the precarity of research positions and over-competition deemed the two most pressing challenges:

In your view, what are the biggest challenges to attractive careers in research currently?

Expectations for Careers in Research

from the Research Community

- **Anneke Kastelein**, PhD Candidate, Leiden University Medical Centre
- **Liz Simmonds**, Head of Research Culture, University of Cambridge
- **Dipti Pandya**, Chair, European Association for Research Managers & Administrators
- Moderator: **Jolanta Šinkūnienė**, Research Council of Lithuania

Focussing on the perspectives of different actors from across the research community, session 1 began with a call to rethink research positions for early-career researchers, allowing talented individuals to 'thrive' rather than 'survive'. Conditions that are common place in other sectors, such as respect for work-life balance, an attractive career outlook, social rights and protection, support for career and personal development, and a pathway to job security could all contribute to a more attractive and sustainable system for early-career researchers. This would incentivise a greater diversity of talented individuals, trained and supported in their early careers, to remain in the public research sector, rather than selecting for those that are able to 'survive' challenging early-career conditions. More career and personal development support is needed, the career pathways that are available to early-career researchers should be better communicated (and advocated), and better framework conditions (long-term funding opportunities, more stable academic positions) should be considered.

Turning to a university perspective on career support and its links to the broader concept of research cultures, it was further emphasised that many early-career researchers endure poor or sub-optimal working conditions and environments because they want an academic career or believe it is the only pathway open to them. The specific reasons for their drive to stay in academia or the research sector – despite unfavorable conditions – are not always well understood. More data are needed on why many leave academia at an early stage and where to, and why some choose to stay. Intersectoral mobility is viewed and often defined by a singular directionality (out of academia and public research), and researchers may feel that they are closing the door on an academic career if they undertake any form of

intersectoral mobility. This perception (currently often correct) reflects broader research culture issues such as the prevalent 'publish or perish' attitude. Research precarity remains a key issue for early-career researchers, characterised by both short-term contracts as well as open-ended contracts with limited funding. Project-based research funding also contributes to precarity where no follow-on support is considered, or where research performing organisations offer positions only from a project-based and low-cost work force perspective. The concept of 'roving researchers' was presented as a good practice example to address these challenges ([University of Cambridge Roving Researcher Scheme](#)), whereby researchers are mobile and not tied to specific projects or roles and can fill positions in a more flexible and continuous way as short-term positions become available (maternity or paternity leave, as example). This roving role, may be attractive to early-career researchers, exposing them to new skills and experiences, but should be implemented carefully and transparently.

Expanding the discussion to other important roles within the broad concept of a research professional, attention turned to research managers, and the extension of the recognition and value of research managers in national and international research systems. Research managers play a critical role in supporting and enabling effective research systems. The roles, responsibilities, and competencies of managers is now being better recognised, in line with the movement towards a more collaborative and 'team' perspective to research projects. Within the umbrella term of a 'research manager', many more specific roles and skills are covered, but greater communication and advocacy are needed to promote these pathways as attractive possibilities, available to all research professionals. In this way, the same

career and personal development opportunities that are called for for early-career researchers should also be made available to and incentivised for (early-career) research managers. Further, research funding and research performing organisations need to work together to better support and integrate these roles into research systems across Europe.

During the panel discussion for session 1, the following questions and points were raised and discussed:

- How can research performing and funding organisations guide research cultures in a direction that adequately recognises and values career pathway diversity away from the perspective that an academic track is the only desirable direction for early-career researchers?
- Research organisations are driving the recognition of a broader set of skills, competencies, and roles in the research sector, in line with [commitments 1 and 2 of the CoARA Agreement](#), with the implementation of narrative CVs (or narrative sections of applications) given as a good practice example that could be more broadly supported and implemented.
- (Early-career) researchers should be enabled to engage in research policy discussions as a means of strengthening the research community voice towards research organisations and policy makers.
- The need to support actions with adequate funding, recognising that many of the system level issues are either directly or indirectly a result of inadequate funding for (inter)national public research systems.
- How can career support and development opportunities for all research professionals be better integrated into research funding opportunities? And what role can RFOs play in encouraging and supporting universities and RPOs to take a more holistic and integrated perspective of the careers of the research professionals they employ?
 - The further enabling of research management roles linked to human resources support may be key in this regard.

Expectations for Careers in Research

Looking Within and Beyond Academia

- **Giorgio Chiarelli**, Research Director, National Institute for Nuclear Physics, Italy
- **Verity Elston**, Co-Director, Graduate Campus, University of Lausanne
- **Conor O'Carroll**, Founder and Director, SciPol Services Ltd, Ireland
- Moderator: **Anjana Buckow**, German Research Foundation

The second session placed the spotlight on the intersection between academic and non-academic career pathways, as well as on intersectoral mobility. Initial perspectives were provided from a domain-specific research performing organisation (the Italian National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN)) that builds close ties to innovation and industry. An example was provided of a specific scheme to nurture entrepreneurial thinking in early-career researchers through a 'Next Generation Entrepreneur' development scheme. Although small in scale, all spin-off projects that were supported led to successful industry applications and relevance. Accompanying this, a specific programme to support technology transfer has also been implemented to promote the transition of research ideas and projects with potential applications towards innovation. Another important perspective and challenge addressed by INFN is the gender gap in physics. Positive action measures such as awards and fellowships for women researchers, mentoring programmes, the expansion of medical insurance provisions to cover pregnancy-related issues up to maternity, and additional financial support during maternity leave and for nursery school cover, have all been implemented in recent years. Collectively, these help to create conditions that are more attractive to women researchers in the field of physics, contributing to a more diverse and inclusion culture and a better and more productive working environment for all.

Focussing on graduate support services, good practice examples and perspectives from the Graduate Campus at the University of Lausanne were provided. Despite a broad suite of support tools and mechanisms available to graduates and early-career researchers, it remains a major challenge to garner interest and participation in career- and professional development services.

This, again, is linked to a culture that does not adequately value these types of activities, and instead focusses the attention of early-career professionals only on core research and academic activities. Efforts to provide and incentivise career- and personal development support services cover four main areas: institutional support for doctoral education and post-doctoral career development; a focus on transparency and communication around diverse career pathways available after the doctoral stage; guidance for both early-career researchers and their supervisors on integrating career and personal development activities and perspectives; and, the provision of tools to enable and manage career development processes and actions.

Following two institutional perspectives, a more personal story was provided on the transition from academia to industry and the conditions that provoked and enabled it. A key aspect and driver for intersectoral mobility that is not understood well enough is the recognition that doctoral training and early-career research activities provide experience, expertise, and skills that are highly transferable. Working in a laboratory requires high levels of teamwork, co-ordination, and management. Performing literature reviews requires self-organisation, information management, and advanced text analysis. These are just two of many examples of the transferable skills that are developed in academia and are highly sought-after in other sectors, but not communicated or nurtured through research support mechanisms adequately. The role of 'protected time' was emphasised as a simple but key means to better recognise and value the importance of career and personal development at all stages in research career trajectories, and also as a means to both improve the attractiveness of

academic career pathways and to promote inter-sectoral mobility.

In the panel discussion for this session, the following questions and discussion points were raised:

- The important role that senior researchers and leaders can take in promoting career and personal development, and how to support them as part of the concept of mentorship. One example might be to require leadership statements for senior positions or through established-researcher grant programmes. This also requires a change in culture, and the next generation of research leaders will likely be more aware of the value and importance of transferable skills.
- The role that data and evidence play in advancing research policies and practices around careers in research. Evidence-based policy making is vital and must be taken into account in all system or organisation-level adaptations. However, organisations and national systems should not wait for evidence to begin acting on key issues. Funding, supporting, and engaging in experiments and pilots is one practical way in which research organisations can drive change.
- How can research organisations address the inherent imbalance between offering and incentivising opportunities for all types of mobility, and the reality that some research professionals do not want to, or cannot, engage with them for personal reasons?
 - This is an important consideration to avoid incorporating bias or unfair treatment into the research system.
- Support mechanisms, mentoring, and giving a voice to early-career researchers are all key actions to enable a career-centred perspective throughout the research sector.
- Opportunities that offer early-career researchers exposure to other sectors would be an effective way to recognise transferable skills and promote career path diversity, and would be relevant to all research domains. This can be implemented through collaborative PhD schemes, industry placements, intersectoral training programmes, or organised site visits, as examples.

Expectations for Careers in Research

from Policy Makers and International Voices

- **Vinciane Gaillard**, Deputy Director of R&I, European University Association
- **Manuel Aleixo**, Head of Unit, DG RTD, European Commission
- **Claudia Sarrico**, OECD Research & Innovation Careers Observatory, Project Lead
- Moderator: **Sean Sapcariu**, Luxembourg National Research Fund

An international and policy-oriented perspective on careers in research was discussed in session 3. Beginning with the perspective of universities across Europe, it was emphasised that the broad concept of academic careers was of strategic importance throughout the continent. It is a main focus of the activities of the European University Association (EUA) Council for Doctoral Education, which contributes to the development of doctoral education and research training across Europe by providing an international platform for collaboration, good practice sharing, and mutual learning. As a basis for collaboration on this topic, a set of shared, core values is key. The EUA is now incorporating an academic and R&I-cultures perspective into its activities, which will be essential to ongoing actions to support academic careers. This is also a focus of the [CoARA Working Group on Reforming Academic Assessment](#). The work goes hand-in-hand with activities to amplify the societal impact of research and education, and advocacy for an effectively designed, managed, and governed R&I system in Europe. More specifically, calls were made to reconsider the effective duration of support for doctoral candidacies, which are often limited to 3 years when the time taken to complete is regularly 4–5 years. This is a big initial contributor to the precarity of research systems, and reduces diversity. A long-term international perspective is needed to support flexible and diverse career pathways, and adequate funding must be provided to support necessary actions.

An EU policy perspective was provided on a range of actions and initiatives that aim to improve the attractiveness of careers in research across the EU and beyond. The European Research Area (ERA) Forum and Policy Agenda remains a vital platform to advance initiatives to support careers in research, including the development of

the [European Framework for Research Careers](#), the [ERA Talent platform](#), and the [ReICO project](#) (expanded upon below). There are important links being made to other ERA-related initiatives, particularly ERA Action 3 on Research Assessment Reform and [CoARA](#). It was emphasised that the time is right to push for accelerated and more profound action to support careers in research across Europe with a new Commission and Commissioner for Research and Innovation as of late 2024, and a new Framework Programme (FP10) looming. A call was made to all stakeholders to voice their support for- and engage with actions that will help to push the shared careers in research agenda forwards. There are also activities underway regarding an ERA Act, and discussion is needed on how legislation at an EU level may be used to improve the conditions for careers in research across EU Member States. These are all initiatives that require support from and engagement with RFOs and RPOs, as well as the research community more broadly. By collaborating and offering a unified voice on key issues, EU-level platforms and tools can be leveraged to support careers in the research sector most effectively.

A status update and summary of the recently launched international data gathering project termed the [Research and Innovation Careers Observatory](#) was provided. ReICO is a joint initiative by the OECD and the EU to address the international lack of relevant data and evidence gaps on many aspects of R&I careers. It will offer dashboards and analytical tools to interrogate available data. The project started in 2024 and will run until 2030. Importantly, the project will use an expanded definition of the R&I workforce to include all types of research professionals. The objective is to collect diverse data from the Innovation sector as well, although this comes with challenges around the definition of common

roles and positions. Questions remain open as to where to draw the line on data collection and what the essential targets are. On the challenges facing R&I careers, there was agreement that attractive working conditions are essential to retaining talent. Equity in careers, and career development support is also a key issue on an international scale regarding talent support. Finally, global mobility was identified as an area where careful consideration and balancing are needed to promote brain circulation in support of collaboration and research quality, whilst preventing brain drain from certain regions. Research organisations are encouraged to participate in – and support the efforts of – the Observatory through existing networks and the ‘Friends of ReICO community’.

In the Q&A panel session, the following discussion points and questions were raised:

- What is the role of research organisations and policy makers in ensuring a balance between collaboration and competition with regards to talent retention and brain circulation?
 - This is a key concern and priority at a European level and across national systems linked to both systems-level excellence support and widening perspectives. An international approach to collective support for national systems is key, as is the

concept of competitiveness through collaboration. A teams-based approach to research conduct, funding, and support will also boost competitiveness and quality.

- Data collection on equality, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) elements beyond gender and age are needed to bolster the collective evidence base for careers in research. For example, socio-economic background information of the existing research workforce (where it is possible to collect) would be highly valuable in determining and developing positive action measures to improve diversity.
- There is a need to focus on and improve human resources management and financial management across the research sector in Europe, and insights, good practices, and lessons learned from other sectors may be useful.
- Finally, and in common with calls from other sessions, the importance of safeguarding, advocating, and expanding R&I budgets both nationally across Europe and at EU level is vital to effective support for all aspects of careers in research. A re-emphasis of the call for 3% of gross domestic product (GDP) to be devoted to R&I systems across all EU Member States was made.

Roundtable Discussion

between Speakers and Science Europe Member Organisations

- Moderated by **Goda Naujokaitytė**, EU Funding Editor, Science Business

Reflecting on the perspectives provided during the initial sessions, there was consensus on the major challenges that need to be addressed: precarity, a lack of career pathway diversity, over-competition, misincentives, and lack of recognition of – and support for – diverse skills and competencies. Several other challenges were raised, including a lack of appropriate data and evidence to inform future support actions, inadequate support for research professionals to engage with career and personal development services, and a lack of awareness of the opportunities and career pathways that exist both within and outside of academia.

Two framework questions arose from the discussions in the first three sessions: 1) how can research systems make better use of the funding available to them? – a pressing question at a time when national research & innovation budgets across Europe are under strain and at risk of cuts – and 2) how can research stakeholders work collaboratively to provide, support, and advocate more flexible and diverse approaches to research career trajectories for all research professionals?

Moving to discussions on the links between research career actions and the ongoing reform of research assessment movement (through the [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment \(CoARA\)](#)), it was agreed that there are many cross-cutting and interdependent issues. Yet, there is not enough shared action between those trying to advance policies and practices around research assessment reform and careers in research. Career pathways are broadly viewed in a very traditional sense, with a narrow uni-directional path from doctoral training to professorship. In reality, very few doctoral candidates follow this path for a variety of reasons. This traditional perspective on career trajectories is linked with a traditional approach to research and researcher assessment processes, and there is opportunity to create positive change as part of the ongoing CoARA movement for careers as well. More emphasis on career and professional development is needed, and research organisations and senior research staff should promote engagement with these services, particularly towards early-career researchers.

Although RFOs carry significant influence on career trajectories available in the public research sector, RPOs must be central to actions to diversify career pathways. There needs to be a clear and transparent separation in the responsibilities of research professional employers (RPOs) and funders (RFOs). In each national system, these responsibilities should be clarified within the frame of existing national legislation, and collaborative actions should be determined to promote national change. These changes will be country-specific, recognising that European countries take quite different approaches to career advancement in research and academia, and changes in legislation might be needed in some national systems. At all levels, a change in culture around careers in research is needed in order to establish career-wide perspectives on available pathways rather than the current system which often focusses on jobs and funded projects as non-connected stages. In all cases, the research community needs to be centrally involved in the development and implementation of policy and practice changes to enable a more diverse perspective on career trajectories for all research professionals (as is the case for the reform of research assessment movement).

The issue of 'protected time', raised during session 2 was further discussed. It was agreed that this was a useful mechanism allowing researchers to improve their skills and focus attention on their longer-term career rather than just their immediate project or function. It was recognised, however, that this time is often not valued or enforced, and there is a culture that disincentivises career and personal development activities. If 'protected time' should be supported further, then it needs to be extended to all research professionals, not just researchers. Linked to this is the linear career path mindset that is pervasive across the research system (as manifested through the R1 to R4 categorisations). More flexibility is needed, allowing some researchers and research professionals to remain at a certain stage while others progress, but still recognising the increased skills, experiences, and real-world career progression of all. Universities and research performing organisations can play a key role in this regard, where

early-career positions are sometimes viewed as low-cost manpower rather than development steps for future leaders and senior professionals. Career development plans may help with culture change on this issue. The principle of life-long learning in research and academia should also be explored more broadly, and an example developed by [Ghent University](#) was provided as an interest case reference.

On the need for more data and evidence to inform policy and practice changes and support careers in research, it was agreed that a more holistic view of national and international R&I systems is needed, including all research professionals and not just researchers. Possibly also including, where possible, professionals who have left academia or the research sector entirely. There is also a need to better integrate more equality, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) related data, as was previously called for in the Science Europe [Practical Guide to Supporting Diversity in Research Environments](#) (2024). When considering expanding data collection exercises, it is important that interoperability and comparability internationally are a key focus, recognising the mobility that is embedded across the research sector. There needs to be a broad discussion across stakeholders on the value and potential impact of contributing to international data collection, yet data should not preclude action on key issues such as precarity.

Although the [Frascati manual](#) provides an international approach to a common understanding of what researchers, research professionals, and research careers are, it remains unclear how these roles are interpreted and implemented at national levels. Further, there is currently no clear picture of what the common and different roles supported by RFOs and RPOs are between national systems. This question arises in recognition of the different competencies and areas of responsibility that RFOs and RPOs play across national systems in Europe and beyond. Clarity at individual organisation level on the specific roles that research organisations do and do not support in national research systems may help to establish a more integrated and holistic perspective of career support for the research sector.

Based on the input received across all four sessions, Science Europe will further discuss potential actions for RFOs and RPOs in several areas, including the following:

- International agreement on a set of minimum standards for careers in research according to career stage or function.

- Fostering a greater valuing and recognition of engagement with career and personal development exercises for all research professionals.
 - Including but not limited to the further roll-out of the 'protected time' concept.
- Expanding and further embedding the concept of career development plans, and their interoperability across career stages, organisations, and national systems.
- Supporting the collection of more and higher-quality data on careers in research across the entire R&I landscape, including promoting discussions on the value of this data to RFOs, RPOs, and national competent authorities.
 - Promoting greater interoperability and comparability of such data internationally.
 - Recognising and supporting efforts already underway such as the [Research and Innovation Careers Observatory](#) internationally, and national efforts such as the [Swiss National Science Foundation Career Tracker Cohort Study](#) and the [FNRS Observatory of Scientific Research and Careers](#) in Belgium as examples.
- Actions to support a multi-stakeholder approach further embedding the 'research professional' concept into the research system, where researchers and research-enabling staff are considered collectively at an ecosystem level and from a career pathway diversity and mobility perspective.
- Actions to better integrate a 'careers in research' perspective into ongoing international research policy movements such as CoARA and the open science movement.
 - Recognising and building on the work already being carried out in this regard through activities such as the [CoARA Working Group on Academic Career Assessment](#), or EU-funded projects such as [SECURE](#), [OPUS](#), [Grasp-OS](#), and [CoARA Boost](#).

Next Steps

The Science Europe Task Force on Research Careers (see Annex 4) will now further discuss the potential action areas proposed across all sessions of the workshop, and will formulate a set of practical recommendations, to be published late 2025 alongside the establishment of a platform or forum to support the implementation of actions by Science Europe Member Organisations. This will contribute to improving the conditions for talented individuals within the research sector in Europe, increasing the quality and impact of research and promote attractive, open, and inclusive research cultures.

Finally, as with all activities conducted under Science Europe's strategic priority on research cultures, engagement with all relevant stakeholders will be undertaken prior to the finalisation of a recommendations, recognising that the topic of careers in research impacts and should be shaped by all research stakeholders.

Annex 1

Workshop Programme

Monday 4 November – Open Webinar

- 14.00–14.05** **Welcome Address**
- Lidia Borrell-Damián, Secretary General, Science Europe
- 14.05–14.15** **Introduction to the Workshop Concept**
- James Morris, Senior Policy Officer, Science Europe
- 14.15–15.15** **Expectations for careers in research from the research community**
- Anneke Kastelein, PhD Candidate, Leiden University Medical Centre
 - Liz Simmonds, Head of Research Culture, University of Cambridge
 - Dipti Pandya, Chair, European Association for Research Managers & Administrators
- Q&A + Discussion (*facilitated by Mentimeter, 30 mins*)
- Moderated by Jolanta Šinkūnienė, Research Council of Lithuania
- 15.15–15.30** *Break*
- 15.30–16.30** **Expectations for careers in research looking within and beyond academia**
- Giorgio Chiarelli, Research Director, National Institute for Nuclear Physics, Italy
 - Verity Elston, Co-Director, Graduate Campus, University of Lausanne
 - Conor O'Carroll, Founder and Director, SciPol Services Ltd, Ireland
- Q&A + discussion (*facilitated by Mentimeter, 30 mins*)
- Moderated by Anjana Buckow, German Research Foundation
- 16.30–17.30** **Expectations on careers in research from policy makers and international voices**
- Manuel Aleixo, Head of Unit, DG RTD, European Commission
 - Claudia Sarrico, OECD Research & Innovation Careers Observatory, Project Lead
 - Vinciane Gaillard, Deputy Director of R&I, European University Association
- Q&A + discussion (*facilitated by Mentimeter, 30 mins*)
- Moderated by Sean Sapcariu, Luxembourg National Research Fund
- 17.30** **Concluding Remarks Day 1**
- James Morris, Senior Policy Officer, Science Europe

Tuesday 5 November – Closed Roundtable

- 09.30–09.40** **Welcome & Recap**
- James Morris, Senior Policy Officer, Science Europe
- 09.40–09.50** **Introduction to session**
- Goda Naujokaitytė, EU Funding Editor, Science Business
 - Sean Sapcariu, Luxembourg National Research Fund
- 09.50–11.00** **Moderated discussion (Part 1)**
Speakers + Science Europe Members + Invited stakeholders
- Moderated by Goda Naujokaitytė, EU Funding Editor, Science Business
- 11.00–11.20** *Break*
- 11.20–12.30** **Moderated discussion (Part 2)**
Speakers + Science Europe Members + Invited stakeholders
- Moderated by Goda Naujokaitytė, EU Funding Editor, Science Business
- 12.30** **Concluding Remarks**
- James Morris, Senior Policy Officer, Science Europe
 - Lidia Borrell-Damián, Secretary General, Science Europe

Annex 2

Selection of Key Studies, Reports, and Policy Papers

The list below represents a non-exhaustive selection of key studies, reports, and policy papers that informed the development and scope of the Science Europe workshop on careers in research:

- DORA (2012). *The San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment*: <https://sfdora.org/read/>
- Science Europe (2016). *Postdoctoral Funding Schemes in Europe*: <https://scieur.org/post-doc-survey>
- Wellcome (2020). *What researchers think about the culture they work in*: <https://wellcome.org/sites/default/files/what-researchers-think-about-the-culture-they-work-in.pdf>
- Aubert Bonn & Pinxten (2021). *Advancing science or advancing careers? Researchers' opinions on success indicators*. PLOS One 16(2): e0243664: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0243664>
- De Herde, Björnalm, & Susi (2021). *Game over: Empower early career researchers to improve research quality*. Insights: the UKSG Journal 34, 1–6: <https://hdl.handle.net/2268/308575>
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Annex 3

Speakers & Contributors

Lidia Borrell-Damián
SECRETARY GENERAL OF SCIENCE EUROPE

Lidia Borrell-Damián is Secretary General of Science Europe, the association representing national public organisations based in countries in the Council of Europe that fund and perform research. She holds overall responsibility for the organisation's strategic development and implementation.

Her areas of experience cover a wide range of Research and Innovation policy priorities, namely EU Framework Programme; European Research Area; International Co-operation; research infrastructures; research ethics and integrity; research assessment processes; university-business co-operation; regional innovation; gender and diversity; Open Science; doctoral education; energy science policy. Concerning international research co-operation, she is engaged in diverse policy fora including: the Global Research Council (GRC), supra-national bodies (UN; OECD-GSF; CoARA; DORA), and well-established international conferences (STS; FAPM; World Science Forum).

She holds a Doctorate in Chemistry (Chemical Engineering: specialty Solar Energy) from the University of Barcelona (1995). She worked at the European University Association (EUA) during 2006–2019, serving the last five years as the Director for R&I. She was Director of Research at Universitat Pompeu Fabra, (Barcelona, Spain, 2003–2005). Formerly, she was a Visiting Scholar at the University of Western Ontario (London, Canada, 1999–2001) and at North Carolina State University (Raleigh, USA, 1997–1998). She was an Assistant Professor at the University of Barcelona from 1990–1998.

James Morris
SENIOR POLICY OFFICER, SCIENCE EUROPE

James Morris is a Senior Policy Officer at Science Europe working broadly on the topics of Research Culture, Research Assessment, and Research Infrastructures. He joined Science Europe in 2019, and has a background in marine and molecular biology and a strong interest in science communication. Before joining Science Europe he was a Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions post-doctoral fellow at the Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences.

Anneke Kastelein
PHD CANDIDATE, LEIDEN UNIVERSITY MEDICAL CENTRE

Anneke Kastelein is a PhD candidate at Leiden University Medical Center. Her research focuses on the mechanisms underlying cancer-related fatigue, integrating chronobiology and oncology to improve cancer patients' quality of life. Beyond research, Anneke has a special interest in bridging the gap between science and policy. She is currently an advisory board member of the PhD representative Network of the Netherlands (PNN).

Liz Simmonds

HEAD OF RESEARCH CULTURE, UNIVERSITY OF CAMBRIDGE

Liz is the Head of Research Culture at the University of Cambridge, responsible for driving the research culture agenda across the institution. She co-chairs the Research Culture Steering Committee, setting the strategy and priorities for research culture. She also works with universities, funders and other stakeholders nationally and internationally to help build a collaborative approach to tackling research culture across the HE sector.

Liz has worked at the University of Cambridge for more than 15 years, primarily in roles supporting early-career researchers. She has a degree in Natural Sciences from the University of Cambridge.

Dipti Pandya

CHAIR, EUROPEAN ASSOCIATION FOR RESEARCH MANAGERS & ADMINISTRATORS

Dipti Pandya serves as the Chair of the European Association for Research Managers and Administrators (EARMA). An active member since 2016, she has held several key roles, including Chair of the EARMA Policy and Representation Committee and elected Board member since 2022. Dipti represents EARMA on ERA Action 17: "Empowering the Research Management Profession". She is dedicated to elevating the recognition of research management as a desirable career of choice in Europe, engaging in initiatives that advance the profession. Her passion lies in fostering collaboration among national and international stakeholders, advocating the profession at the highest levels, and driving innovations that enhance the community's impact on the research landscape.

As the Director of Research at University College Dublin (UCD), Dipti leads the UCD Research Unit in developing a comprehensive research strategy and cultivating relationships to support the university's ambitious research goals. She prioritises enhanced support throughout the entire research project lifecycle for the UCD research community. Prior to her appointment in 2024, she served as Head of Pre-award Funding, overseeing the EU, national, and international funding advisory and contract teams. Dipti established the UCD EU Research Office and the ERC Talent Team, which have significantly contributed to UCD's ranking as No. 1 in Ireland and among the Top 25 in the EU for Horizon Europe.

Dipti has also been appointed by the Irish Minister for Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science to the board of Léargas and previously served on the board of the Irish Universities Quality Board. Before joining UCD, she was the Director of the Irish Research Council for Humanities and Social Sciences. Her extensive experience encompasses all aspects of the research funding lifecycle, including roles as an Erasmus Alumni, EC Stagiaire, funded researcher, expert evaluator, national delegate for SSH, EU Research Infrastructures Advisory Group member, senior research manager, and funder.

Jolanta Šinkūnienė

PROFESSOR IN LINGUISTICS AND A DIRECTOR OF THE INSTITUTE OF ENGLISH, ROMANCE AND CLASSICAL STUDIES AT VILNIUS UNIVERSITY

Dr Jolanta Šinkūnienė is a professor in linguistics and a director of the Institute of English, Romance and Classical Studies at Vilnius University, Lithuania. She is also a member of the Expert committee of Humanities and Social Sciences at the Research Council of Lithuania as well as a co-chair of Research Culture group at Science Europe. Jolanta's research interests focus on academic rhetoric, disciplinary cultures, research publication practices, evaluation of research, academic identity aspects.

Giorgio Chiarelli

RESEARCH DIRECTOR, NATIONAL ITALIAN INSTITUTE FOR NUCLEAR PHYSICS

Giorgio Chiarelli is an experimental physicist in High Energy Physics, and Research Director at the National Institute for Nuclear Physics, Italy (INFN). Since 2012, his research activity shifted to experiments ongoing at CERN. He has been involved in evaluation of research, and of impact of research on society in Italy and outside since the mid-2000s. He has participated in the Science Europe Working Groups on Research Evaluation and Research Culture, including the Task Force that developed the 'Position Statement and Recommendations on Research Assessment Processes'. ANVUR (the Italian agency for evaluation of research), charged Giorgio to co-ordinate the group of experts charged to evaluate the 'Production of Public Goods' as part of research evaluation exercises between 2011–2014. In 2017, he succeeded in creating a Third Mission committee to co-ordinate INFN activities towards societal challenges, and lead this structure until 2023.

Verity Elston

CO-DIRECTOR, GRADUATE CAMPUS, UNIVERSITY OF LAUSANNE

Verity Elston is co-director of the Graduate Campus at the University of Lausanne, where she leads support for the career and professional development for early-career researchers across seven faculties. She has been working for over 15 years in the field, first at the EPFL Doctoral School in Lausanne, and then for the Conference of Western Swiss Universities, before joining the University of Lausanne with the creation of the Graduate Campus in 2017. Her background informs the work she does: after several years working in the public and private sectors in several countries, she returned to university in Ireland to complete her Bachelors degree, and followed with a PhD in Anthropology at the University of Chicago. Throughout, her core question has been how to best provide supportive frameworks for the professional development of doctoral and postdoctoral researchers, and for the people who manage them.

Conor O'Carroll
FOUNDER & DIRECTOR, SCIPOL SERVICES, IRELAND

Dr. Conor O'Carroll is founder and director of SciPol Services Ltd. As an independent consultant on Research and Higher Education policy and funding, he focuses on researchers' career development with special attention to doctoral education and career assessment. He is a lead assessor for HRS4R and has worked on the revision of the European Researchers Charter and Code. He has led European policy initiatives on Open Science and doctoral training (e.g., the development of the European Innovative Doctoral Training Principles and the European Framework for Research Careers). He is an active researcher on national and European Research Policy, R&D, Higher Education and Researcher Mobility policy and is an accomplished commentator on R&D and higher education policy and funding. He is currently chair of the EC Mutual Learning Exercise on Research Careers

Anjana Buckow
PROGRAMME DIRECTOR OF RESEARCH CAREERS, DFG

At the head office of the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG), Anjana Buckow oversees Research Careers issues. That includes, among other things, analysing the need for adjustments of the DFG's funding portfolio for early-career researchers and informing the target group about the funding opportunities provided by the DFG. Anjana has worked for the DFG for over 20 years. She has a degree in Contemporary History from the Martin Luther University at Halle/Saale.

Manuel Aleixo
HEAD OF UNIT, DG RTD, EUROPEAN COMMISSION

Manuel Aleixo, currently Head of Unit A2 – ERA, Spreading Excellence and Research Careers, in DG Research and Innovation, European Commission; previously assistant to the Director-General of DG R&I, and before that member of cabinet of the Commissioner responsible for Research, Science and Innovation, Carlos Moedas.

Claudia Sarrico
PROJECT LEAD, OECD RESEARCH AND INNOVATION CAREERS OBSERVATORY

Cláudia S. Sarrico is a policy analyst at the OECD Science, Technology, and Innovation Directorate. She is the project manager of the Research and Innovation Careers Observatory project. Previously she was the project manager of the OECD Global Science Forum projects on Reducing the Precarity of Academic Research Careers and Promoting Diverse Career Pathways of Doctoral and Postdoctoral Researchers.

Before joining the OECD, she was a Professor at the School of Economics and Management of the University of Minho, and a senior researcher at the Centre for Research on Higher Education Policies, Portugal. She holds a PhD in Industrial and Business Studies from Warwick Business School.

Vinciane Gaillard
DEPUTY DIRECTOR OF R&I, EUROPEAN UNIVERSITY ASSOCIATION

Vinciane is Deputy Director for Research and Innovation at EUA. She is responsible for EUA's comprehensive approach to the transition to Open Science. As such, Vinciane oversees the Association's work to help its members transition to Open Science, contribute to the development of national, European and institutional policies conducive to the mainstreaming of Open Science and encourage universities to play a proactive role in the regulatory and financial frameworks shaping this process.

Prior to joining EUA in 2019, Vinciane worked as a scientist and then as research manager in the field of cognitive psychology/neurosciences for more than fifteen years. She holds a doctorate in Psychology from the Université libre de Bruxelles (ULB), Belgium. Photo credit : Aude Vanlathem.

Sean Sapcariu
PROGRAMME MANAGER OF STRATEGIC PROGRAMMES & RESEARCH CULTURE, FNR

Sean Sapcariu is a programme manager at the Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR), responsible for strategic programmes and research culture initiatives. He has led the implementation of a narrative CV template across FNR funding programmes, co-produced a video with DORA giving guidance to evaluators on responsible research assessment techniques, and helped organise the 2021 Science Europe High Level Workshop on Research Culture. Internationally, he sits on the DORA Steering Committee, the GRC Working Group on Responsible Research Assessment, and co-chairs the Science Europe Working Group on Research Culture. Before joining the FNR, Sean completed his PhD studies at the University of Luxembourg in Biology and worked as a Liaison Officer in the Strategy and Planning Office of the University of Luxembourg Rectorate.

Goda Naujokaitytė
EU FUNDING EDITOR, SCIENCE|BUSINESS

Goda joined Science|Business in April 2020. Previously, she interned at the Council of the European Union and the Guardian News Media, among other organisations in the UK and Lithuania. Goda holds a bachelor's degree in communication from the University of Nottingham and a Master's degree in data journalism from Cardiff University.

Annex 4

Task Force on Research Careers

This workshop was conceived and developed by the Science Europe Office and the Science Europe Task Force on Research Careers. The Task Force is co-ordinated by James Morris, Senior Policy Officer at Science Europe.

Current Task Force Members

Name	Organisation	Country
Sapcariu, Sean	Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
Van Acker, Frederik	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Valosaari, Kata-Riina	Research Council of Finland (AKA)	Finland
Costa, Rosário	Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal
Chiarelli, Giorgio	National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN)	Italy
Ségerie, Audrey	Fund for Scientific Research (FNRS)	Belgium
Györffi, Miklós	Hungarian Research Network (HUN-REN)	Hungary
Olm, Eric	Swedish Research Council (VR)	Sweden
Buckow, Anjana	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Manner, Christina	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Šinkūnienė, Jolanta	Research Council of Lithuania (LMT)	Lithuania

Past Task Force Members

Name	Organisation	Country
Cañibano, Carolina	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Szymańska-Skolimowska, Ewelina	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Schiøtt, Birgit	Danish Council for Independent Research (DFF)	Denmark
Cahenzli, Julia	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland

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Science Europe is the association of major research funding and research performing organisations in Europe.

Our vision is for the European Research Area to have the optimal conditions to support robust education and research & innovation systems.

We define long-term perspectives for European research and champion best-practice approaches that enable high-quality research for knowledge advancement and the needs of society.

We are uniquely placed to lead advancements to the European Research Area and inform global developments through participation in research initiatives where science is a strong and trusted component of sustainable economic, environmental, and societal development.

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